

TEACHING PERFORMANCE OF NEW CLINICAL INSTRUCTORS OF SELECTED SCHOOLS OF NURSING: TOWARDS IMPROVED QUALITY OF INSTRUCTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10886783>

ABSTRACT

This research explores the teaching performance level of new clinical instructors in selected nursing schools within Region 12, Philippines, as perceived by deans and nursing students, against the backdrop of ongoing expectations for nurses to make meaningful societal contributions through their professionalism and competency, a critical success factor in healthcare. Utilizing a descriptive comparative research design, the study assesses perceptions via a questionnaire adapted from the World Health Organization, engaging 313 students and 14 deans through purposive sampling. Results indicate that students perceive their instructors' performance as quite confident across various domains, including adult learning, curriculum design, knowledge maintenance, research skills, communication, professionalism, evaluation, and leadership, with mean scores ranging from 3.64 to 3.85. Conversely, deans' perceptions were notably higher, reflecting very confident assessments with mean scores ranging from 4.09 to 4.69, pointing to a significant difference in perceived performance between deans and students ($p \leq 0.05$). The study concludes with a call for improved communication and alignment between instructors' teaching methods and the expectations of both students and administrative bodies, recommending the development of common assessment tools and continuous performance monitoring to bridge perceptual gaps and enhance teaching quality.

Keywords: *Clinical Instructors, Nursing Education, Teaching Performance, WHO Competencies*

INTRODUCTION

Nurses face ongoing expectations to make meaningful contributions to society through their professional roles. This involves not just administering direct healthcare, but also safeguarding individuals' well-being and aiding in everyday life tasks. To meet these responsibilities effectively, it is crucial for nurses to consistently enhance their skills and competencies and apply them in their everyday professional activities (Fukada, 2018). The role of nursing instructors in hands-on clinical training is crucial for enhancing the practical skills of nursing undergraduates (Gcawu & van Rooyen, 2022). Nurse educators are essential for enhancing the quality of healthcare staff. They act as mentors and offer the required leadership to promote practices based on solid evidence, which in turn helps to better patient results (Gutierrez, 2020).

Given the multifaceted roles and expectations for both practicing nurses and nursing educators, it becomes evident that competency is not just a requirement but a critical factor for success in healthcare. Nurse educators must have a solid competency to respond to evolving health needs (WHO, 2022). Competencies refer to the blend of individual attributes, behaviors, skills, and knowledge needed to execute tasks effectively in a job role (Satoh et al., 2020). For those in academic nursing education, a high level of proficiency is required in various areas, including instruction, scholarly investigation, hands-on clinical work, administrative tasks, effective communication, and ethical conduct (Mikkonen et al., 2018).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2022), nurse educators are expected to be well-versed in modern educational theories and practical applications, especially in curriculum design and adult learning. They must stay updated on current best practices, be skilled in research and problem-solving, and communicate effectively in both educational and clinical settings. Ethics and legal considerations should be integral to their teaching, and they should use diverse evaluation methods to assess both programs and individual student performance. Strong management and leadership skills are also highlighted as essential for maintaining program quality and potentially influencing broader educational policies.

However, even though clinical skills are critical for quality patient care and successful outcomes, previous research has indicated that both practicing nurses and recent nursing graduates sometimes lack adequate competencies (Alavi et al., 2022). Furthermore, there has been limited research focus on the subject matter expertise of nurses as well as how nurse educators approach the teaching and learning aspects of their roles (Zlatanovic et al., 2017). Studies also show that challenges in clinical education have been arising including a mismatch between the expertise of educators and the requirements of internships, a shortage of qualified instructors, students' lack of motivation to learn, poor collaboration among healthcare professionals, and students not being aware of their strengths and weaknesses (Hakim, 2023).

Against this backdrop, the need for competent nurse instructors is more urgent than ever. Given the escalating demands on healthcare and the pivotal role nurses play

in this sector, particularly in the Philippines where the number of nursing graduates is essential, understanding the effectiveness of new clinical instructors is of utmost importance. Thus, the prevailing issues and concern about the competencies of clinical instructors have made the researcher interested in conducting the study, to fill a crucial gap in existing research by focusing on the teaching performance of new clinical instructors in selected nursing schools.

Research Questions

This study determined the teaching performance of new clinical instructors of selected schools of nursing. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How is the level of performance of the new clinical instructor described in terms of:
 - 1.1. Adult Learning
 - 1.2. Curriculum Design
 - 1.3. Knowledge Maintenance
 - 1.4. Research Skills
 - 1.5. Communication
 - 1.6. Professionalism
 - 1.7. Evaluation
 - 1.8. Leadership
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of performance of the new clinical instructors as perceived by the deans and nursing students?
3. What is the implication of the findings of the study to nursing administration?

METHODOLOGY

The study employs a descriptive comparative research design to systematically investigate the teaching performance of new clinical instructors in selected nursing schools. The comparative research design is a strategic approach chosen for this study to enable a systematic comparison between the perceptions of different groups regarding the teaching performance of new clinical instructors in selected nursing schools (Siedlecki, 2020). This design is particularly well-suited for the investigation because it allows for the examination of the similarities and differences in opinions among two key stakeholder groups: deans and nursing students in selected nursing schools in Region 12. Employing purposive sampling, data was collected from a questionnaire adapted from the World Health Organization's (2022) guidelines on evaluating the performance of clinical instructors on 313 nursing students and 14 deans who have interacted with new clinical instructors and consent to participate in the study.

The statistical analysis of the data collected in this study was done using SPSS IBM Statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and mean were used to describe the data, and inferential statistics using a t-test was used to find out the significant differences among the variables. Ethical considerations were strictly followed in the conduct of the study, with the study obtaining necessary approvals and informed consent, ensuring voluntary participation, anonymity, and confidentiality.

The scope of this study is focused on the teaching performance of new clinical instructors in selected schools of nursing within the researcher's locale. The evaluation was based on WHO core competencies, specifically in the areas of adult learning, curriculum design, knowledge maintenance, research skills, communication, professionalism, evaluation, and leadership. In terms of limitations, the research was confined to selected schools within the researcher's locale, limiting its generalizability to other geographical areas or educational settings. Only the variables stated in the statement of the problem were examined. The period of the study was from A.Y. 2023-2024.

RESULTS

Table 1 reveals the assessment of teaching performance domains as perceived by students and deans.

Table 1. Teaching Performance Domains as Perceived by Students and Deans

Domain	Mean Scores ($\bar{x}$)			
	Students	Interpretation	Dean	Interpretation
Adult Learning	3.64	Quite Confident	4.50	Very Confident
Curriculum Design	3.64	Quite Confident	4.44	Very Confident
Knowledge Maintenance	3.85	Quite Confident	4.69	Very Confident
	3.70	Quite Confident	4.09	Quite Confident
Research Skills				
Communication	3.79	Quite Confident	4.50	Very Confident
Professionalism	3.84	Quite Confident	4.63	Very Confident
Evaluation	3.73	Quite Confident	4.44	Very Confident
Leadership	3.79	Quite Confident	4.44	Very Confident
Overall	3.75	Quite Confident	4.47	Very Confident

(Legend: 4.21-5.00 -Very Confident; 3.41-4.20 - Quite Confident; 2.61-3.40; Moderately Confident; 1.81-2.60 - Slightly Confident; 1.00-1.80 -Not Confident)

While both groups show positive perceptions, the overall mean scores reveal a significant disparity, with students being "Quite Confident" (3.75) and deans "Very Confident" (4.47) in the instructors' teaching performance.

Table 2 presents the results of a comparative analysis of the perceived level of performance of new clinical instructors between deans and students.

Table 2. Differences in the Level of Performance of New Clinical Instructors as Perceived by the Deans and Students

Domain	T-statistics	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Adult Learning	61.515	0.00	Reject null hypothesis	Significant
Curriculum Design	61.278	0.00	Reject null hypothesis	Significant

Knowledge Maintenance	61.538	0.00	hypothesis Reject null hypothesis	Significant
Research Skills	58.156	0.00	hypothesis Reject null hypothesis	Significant
Communication	62.881	0.00	hypothesis Reject null hypothesis	Significant
Professionalism	61.214	0.00	hypothesis Reject null hypothesis	Significant
Evaluation	60.744	0.00	hypothesis Reject null hypothesis	Significant
Leadership	59.53	0.00	hypothesis Reject null hypothesis	Significant

p ≤.05 significant

Deans and students have significantly different perceptions of how well clinical instructors perform in the area of Adult Learning (t=61.515, p≤.05). Deans and students hold also significantly different views on the performance of clinical instructors in terms of curriculum development (t=61.278, p≤.05). For knowledge maintenance (t=61.538, p≤.05), Deans and students have significantly different perceptions regarding clinical instructors' performance in maintaining knowledge. Deans and students have also significantly divergent opinions on the research skills of clinical instructors (t=58.156, p≤.05). There is a significant difference in the perceived level of performance between deans and students in Communication (t=62.881, p≤.05). Moreover, there is a significant difference in the perceived level of performance between deans and students in terms of Professionalism (t=61.214, p≤.05). Lastly, there is a significant difference in the perceived level of performance between deans and students in Leadership (t=59.53, p≤.05).

DISCUSSION

The student assessments of clinical instructors' teaching performance in this study reveal a positive perception, particularly in the application of adult learning principles, curriculum design, and communication skills, reflecting a strong competence in motivating self-directed learning and engaging students in course planning (Saeedi et al., 2021; Haleem et al., 2022). However, there is a noted need for further emphasis on accommodating diverse learning speeds, an essential aspect of effective adult education (McCall et al., 2018). While students displayed confidence in their instructors' knowledge maintenance and research skills, minor gaps in the ability to perform accurate patient assessments and quantitative research skills were identified, aligning with the findings of Vaismoradi et al. (2020) and Bullo et al. (2021). The overall student perception underscores the instructors' proficiency in key educational areas but also highlights areas for development to enhance nursing education and practice.

The deans' assessment mirrors and extends the students' positive evaluation, especially in areas such as adult learning, curriculum design, and knowledge

maintenance, showcasing a high level of confidence in clinical instructors' abilities to foster autonomous learning and utilize technology effectively in education (Chowdhury, 2021; Rodríguez-Almagro et al., 2021). However, slight improvements are needed in collaborative curriculum planning and evidence-based care implementation, resonating with the challenges discussed in Handelzalts (2019) and Lamontagne et al. (2021). Deans also emphasize the significance of research mentorship and effective communication in nursing education, aligning with Gularte-Rinaldo et al. (2023) and Ferrández-Antón et al. (2020). Professionalism and leadership qualities of instructors were highly regarded by deans, with minor areas for enhancement in ethical discussions and broader leadership roles, highlighting the ongoing development needed to meet the evolving demands of nursing education (Haddad & Geiger, 2023; Horstman & Godwin, 2021).

The findings from both student and dean assessments illustrate a comprehensive acknowledgment of clinical instructors' strengths in various educational domains, aligned with the study's objectives to evaluate teaching performance. These results not only corroborate with existing literature by demonstrating the effectiveness of instructor-led motivation and the use of technology in education (Saeedi et al., 2021; Rodríguez-Almagro et al., 2021) but also identify areas for improvement such as recognizing diverse learning speeds and implementing evidence-based care (McCall et al., 2018; Lamontagne et al., 2021). The consistency with other investigations signifies a broad recognition of these competencies and development needs in nursing education. Nevertheless, the noted differences in confidence levels between students and deans suggest varying perspectives on the instructors' effectiveness, underscoring the importance of continuous professional development and adaptive teaching strategies to enhance the quality of nursing education and meet the diverse needs of learners.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, new clinical instructors are highly confident in their teaching performance as viewed by the dean and students. It is further concluded that there is a significant difference in how new clinical instructor's teaching performances are viewed. Overall, the results highlight the need for improved communication and collaboration between deans and students in the assessment of clinical instructors. It is recommended to introduce training and professional development programs for new clinical instructors aimed at refining their teaching abilities in line with both student and dean expectations. To ensure a consistent evaluation of clinical instructor performance, the development and implementation of standardized evaluation criteria and assessment tools, agreed upon by both deans and students, are suggested. This approach would facilitate a unified framework for assessment. Furthermore, establishing a system for the ongoing evaluation and monitoring of clinical instructors, incorporating feedback from both deans and students, will aid in pinpointing areas needing enhancement.

Recommendations

For future research, broadening the study to encompass a wider and more varied sample size and extending its geographical coverage to include multi-region

investigations is recommended. This expansion would provide a more comprehensive insight into the perceptions of clinical instructor performance, potentially uncovering region-specific challenges and best practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Stringent ethical guidelines were upheld to guarantee the study's integrity and participant well-being. Approval was secured from the institutional review board, and informed consent was obtained from all deans and nursing students involved, ensuring their awareness of the study's aims, voluntary participation, and confidentiality. Participant anonymity was maintained by using code numbers for identification, and all data were to be securely deleted post-study. The researcher conducted the study without any conflict of interest, took measures against plagiarism, and ensured objective interpretation of the findings, using the results solely to advance research in nursing education.

Acknowledgements

The researcher extends gratitude to Dr. Lucila O. Sunga, RN, for her invaluable mentorship and guidance, enhancing my growth as a researcher. Appreciation is also directed towards her committee members, Prof. Mary Jane N. Rigor, RN, MSN, Dr. Jerelyn S. Victoriano, RN, and Dr. Joeal M. Lagrimas, RN, RT, for their insightful feedback and support during my defense. A heartfelt thank you is offered to the nursing students and deans from selected Region 12 nursing schools for their cooperation, and to my academic mentors and peers for their advice and support throughout the research process.

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